

ACTIONS NECESSARY TO BE USED IN LESSON PROCESSES TO DEVELOP LINGUISTIC COMPETENCIES IN PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

Tursunkulova Makhfuza Tolkin qizi

Doctoral student of UzSRIPS

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Abstract. *The methods used in the teaching process are of great importance for the development of linguistic competences in elementary school students. This article will discuss this.*

Keywords: *Linguistic competence, mother tongue lessons, concentration, speaking, writing, student's vocabulary.*

As a result of the research on the problem, it became clear how useful it is to use a number of educational games and methods in the formation of scientific competence in mother tongue classes. It was concluded that all of these are the most effective ways to develop the linguistic competence of primary school students in terms of specific vocabulary in their mother tongue classes. And it was concluded that it is necessary to pay strict attention to the content and effectiveness of the methods used in the teaching process.

The fair and democratization of the educational system in our country creates special demands for the educational process and special pedagogical relations. This process is fundamentally different from the previous one. Nowadays, it is known that it is not enough for students to have only knowledge, skills and qualifications in educational subjects. Including: some students who have successfully graduated from an educational institution face many failures in life;

even if a young specialist who graduated from a higher education institution and went to a new job acquired sufficient knowledge and skills related to his profession at an institute or university, it takes a long time to get used to the workplace;

in a critical approach, it becomes clear that the knowledge and skills acquired at school or lyceum do not correspond to life situations that need to be solved quickly or are not needed at all.

According to scientific pedagogical and psychological sources, competence is a common concept for many disciplines. Therefore, its interpretations are different both in size and content, and in terms of meaning and logical content.

First of all, it is important to be able to fully attract the student's attention to the subject or subject in order to thoroughly acquire the necessary knowledge and develop a number of competences related to science. It's no secret that the first type of attention - involuntary attention - is dominant in a child who has just entered school. It can be observed that his attention is quickly divided, he is distracted, he cannot keep himself in one place.

At this time, showing him the things that are important and interesting for the child will increase the child's attention to the shape, appearance, location, size, difference and color of these things. And now the child will be able to hold his mind at one point in relation to the object during the careful study of this object. As a result, he learns what this thing is for and how it is used. Such activities also help the development of the child's memory.

To do this, of course, it is also useful to use psychological exercises and training. Because, first of all, it is necessary to introduce the student to science, to prepare the child for this process before connecting him with science. As a result of the knowledge obtained from a number of research literature and sources, it should be said that it is psychological research that shows that it is somewhat difficult to concentrate the attention of young schoolchildren (ages 7-11). Their attention can be concentrated for 6-7 minutes. After that, students' attention will be divided by itself. During this time, the teacher should provide the students with certain knowledge, skills and abilities, and should carry out educational work. For this, high knowledge and skills are required from the teacher.

Here is an example of a concentration exercise:

We show the student a picture of a bunch of wild animals at the same time.

We ask you to distinguish which of these are birds, which are predators, and which are reptiles.

Then we ask where these animals live and what they eat.

Next time, we will encourage the development of the student's thinking by asking about the concepts of adjectives, such as the color and size of the people in this picture.

After such exercises, the student's attention is focused on one point, and it becomes easier for him to enter the subject, to understand the subject, and it becomes easier to form elements of competence. Also, we need to work separately on the vocabulary and increase the vocabulary in order to form the competence knowledge of the students. Words and phrases are the basic units of language that express meaning. These language units represent specific objects, abstract concepts, emotions-feelings-excitement of an individual. The vocabulary of the language is the sum of all the words and phrases in the language. In this sense, lexicology is a methodical basis for increasing students' vocabulary. Any speech is made up of words and phrases that are grammatically connected and consistent with the content. The richer and more developed a person's vocabulary is, the richer his speech will be. It provides a wide opportunity to express one's opinion clearly, clearly and expressively. Therefore, vocabulary, its diversity, mobility is an important condition for successful development of speech in the methodology.

Any speech is made up of grammatically interconnected words and phrases that match the content in a certain sequence. The richer and more developed a person's vocabulary is, the richer his speech will be. A wide opportunity is created for him to express his opinion clearly and expressively. Therefore, the richness, variety, mobility of the vocabulary is an important condition for the successful development of speech. First of all, the surrounding environment, nature, people's lives, study activities, interactions with adults and peers serve as the main source for the enrichment of the student's vocabulary. As a result of interacting with nature and people, the child learns words, phrases, figurative expressions, proverbs, wise words, and turns them into his own words. Works of art are the most reliable source for enriching students' vocabulary and speech. In the process of familiarizing with and analyzing works of art in the mother tongue and reading literacy classes, students' vocabulary is enriched on certain topics. It is not an exaggeration to say that. For example, in the process of getting to know the topics related to the seasons, if the concepts related to changes in nature, birds, animals, animal world, trees, grass and herbs are formed, then the topics of spirituality, good and evil, friendship by studying the works, he comes to certain conclusions about human relations and ethics. The meaning of the word is not explained while reading the text. If it is necessary, the attention of the students will not be distracted from the

content of the text, but it will be passed with a short explanation. Words used figuratively are explained after reading the text. Because their meaning is better understood from the content of the text. It can be seen that it is important for students to master the vocabulary of the language and make it their property when they acquire the knowledge that is intended to be learned, and when they apply it in practice.

There is no special lesson for working on vocabulary. It is carried out in the study of all subjects, mainly in connection with the teaching of textbook materials in mother tongue classes. Providing lexical knowledge to primary school students is not limited to mother tongue classes, but is also taught during reading classes. In particular, the analysis of the texts given in the native language book in teaching the vocabulary of the language, old and new words, dialectal words, professional words, Russian-international words, Vocabulary work in each lesson is of great importance. Theoretical knowledge is formed through practical work. This is the basis for the development of linguistic competences in elementary school students.

A person acquires certain knowledge and skills through theoretical knowledge. By being able to apply these knowledge and skills in practice, a certain qualification is acquired.

As mentioned above, mother tongue education has been mainly concerned with the development of linguistic competence in students. Linguistic competence of students is their knowledge of the language, the ability to connect this knowledge with practice, and the ability to create speech. If the knowledge given to students on language construction is focused on the development of their oral and written speech, it will serve to form their linguistic competence. Knowledge that is not useful for the improvement of oral and written speech is not part of linguistic competence. In general, the money and time spent on providing linguistic knowledge that is not connected with practice and does not create speaking skills is not justified. For example, the rules of correct pronunciation of foreign words along with the knowledge of accent will develop students' speaking skills. However, the knowledge that the stress of the word falls on the last syllable in Uzbek, and that some adverbs do not receive stress at the end of the word, is not part of linguistic competence. After all, this knowledge does not become a skill. Even if the student does not have them, he will not make a mistake in stressing the syllables in the appropriate places. Knowledge of words is the basis of linguistic competence. The students' vocabulary serves to ensure the accuracy, correctness, fluency and variety of speech. Feeling the word means feeling the mother tongue. It is not for nothing that when comparing the works of artists, the quantity of words used by writers is not considered as one of the main evaluation criteria. Therefore, vocabulary should be the basis of mother tongue linguistic education.

"Word Studies", "Word Magic", "The Power of Words", "Ourselves and Our Words", "The World of Words", "Journey to the World of Words", "Word The separation of sections such as "z sayri" (of course, these are approximate) is not only in a certain grade or in the elementary grade, but in every grade, using words, choosing, replacing words, their new it is necessary to give a great place to activities such as learning the meanings of spelling and pronunciation. Also, working with dictionaries should be increased. Just as the child learns his mother tongue from the language society, he unconsciously learns the basic phonetic, morphological and syntactic rules of the language, which are given as knowledge today. If necessary, we remind them of these rules during the educational process, but we do not need to spend the main attention, time and money on it. A person who speaks his mother tongue, but has not acquired knowledge of it, can never pronounce sounds incorrectly, use adverbs out of place, and make mistakes in the construction of sentences.

But the vocabulary and the ability to use words require a special, comprehensive education. It can be concluded that the science of lexicography should be the basis of linguistic competence. Its priority in the content of mother tongue education is in accordance with the stated goals.

The clash of different cultures in the conditions of globalization requires young people growing up in the situation of national and international communication to have a high communication culture and vocabulary. This requires improvement of mother tongue education, raising the acquired qualifications of students to the level of linguistic competence.

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